

Search for Potential Amoebicides : III. Synthesis of Substituted 2-Hydrazino-5-Sulphazino Quinolines and Their Anils

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Some new substituted 2-hydrazino-5-sulphazino quinolines and a series of anils have been synthesised. All the anils were screened invitro for antiamebic activity against *E. histolytica* (axenic). A majority of them were found to be considerably active.

A large number of quinoline derivatives are the most effective and best tolerated amoebicides known so far¹⁻⁶. Among them, those quinoline moieties with a methoxy or a methyl substituent (at position 8) are the most effective ones. Recently, Misra and Saxena^{6,7} reported some new quinolines having good activity against *E. histolytica* at a conc. of 125 µg/ml.

It has also been observed that a group of anils also exhibit good activity against *E. coli*⁸⁻¹³. Misra and Saxena¹³ and Seth *et al*¹⁴ also prepared a host of anils showing good antiamebic activity. Therefore, the present authors decided to synthesise such anils as are incorporated into substituted quinolines with both sulphazino and hydrazino groups with a view to enhancing amoebicidal activity by synergistic effect of all these moieties.

The 2-carbethoxy-3-methyl-4-hydroxy-8-substituted quinolines were prepared according to Steek *et al*¹⁵. The 2-carbethoxy-3-methyl-4-hydroxy-8-substituted-5 azophenyl quinolines obtained by an earlier method⁷ were condensed with hydrazine hydrate (98%) to obtain the corresponding hydrazino quinolines which on condensation with substituted aromatic aldehydes afforded the desired anils.

Bioassay: A survey of Table 2 indicates that the most active compound was no 15 as its end point correction was 1 : 32000. The next in activity was compound no. 27 which had half its activity. Compounds number 1, 2, 8, 10, 12, 16, 23, 28 and 31 had only one fourth activity when compared to compound no. 15. However, no significant conclusion regarding any structure activity relationship can be drawn on the basis of these results except for the observation that a 1, 3 diazino moiety (compound 15) is probably responsible for the significant activity specially when the anil position had a ortho hydroxy phenyl substituent. If an ortho chlorophenyl or cinnamyl group were present instead of

o-hydroxy-phenyl, the activity was either lost or diminished.

Experimental

3-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-azophenyl-8-methyl.

2-quinolinoyl hydrazines: 2-carbethoxy-3-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-azophenyl-8-methyl quinoline (0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (98% ; 0.015 mole) were taken in a 100 ml. flask to which absolute ethanol (25 ml.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 3 hr. on a steam bath. The solid obtained after removal of the solvent was washed with a little water and recrystallised from 80% ethanol.

The four hydrazines thus prepared are reported in Table I.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R ₁	m.p. °C
1.	-guanidino	224
2.	-1, 3-diazino	230
3.	-dimidino	222
4.	-acetamido	220

Anils of 3-methyl, 4-hydroxy, 5-azophenyl, 8-methyl, 2-quinolinoyl hydrazines :

Equimolar proportions of a 3-methyl, 4-hydroxy, 5-azophenyl, 8-methyl quinolinoyl hydrazine and an aromatic aldehyde were refluxed in ethanol for an hour. On cooling a solid was obtained which was recrystallised from ethanol.

All the compounds prepared and their antiamoebic activities against *E. Histolytica* are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Antiamoebic activity against <i>E. histolytica</i> . End point concentration.
R₁ = -guanidino			
1.	C ₆ H ₅	242	1:8000
2.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	220	1:8000
3.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	225	1:1000
4.	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	226	non-active
5.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	245	1:1000
6.	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	243	1:1000
7.	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	210	1:1000
8.	4-OH, 3OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	234	1:8000
9.	3, 4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	220	1:4000
10.	3, 4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -6NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	250	1:8000
11.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	235	1:2000
12.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	235	1:8000
13.	4-NH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	240	1:1000
R₁ = -1, 3-diazino.			
14.	C-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	225	non-active
15.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	219	1:32000
16.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	220	1:8000
R₁ = -dimidino			
17.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	222	1:1000
18.	3-OH, 4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	234	non-active
19.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	213	1:1000
20.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	216	non-active
21.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	219	1:1000
22.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	234	1:1000
23.	3, 4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	220	non-active
24.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	230	non-active

Table 2 (Contd.)

R ₁ = -acetamido			
25.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	200	1:1000
26.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	192	1:2000
27.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	222	1:16000
28.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	221	1:8000
29.	3, 4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	218	1:1000
30.	4 (CH ₃) ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	228	1:4000
31.	3, 4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -6NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	260	1:8000

*All melting points are uncorrected.

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